

ATLANTIC REMOTE SENSING LAND OCEAN EXPERIMENT (ARSLOE)

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ABSTRACT

ARSLOE was a multi-organization experiment held October 6 to November 30, 1980, near Duck, North Carolina. It provided a large number of wind-wave and related measurements to intercompare and develop wave measurement systems and to evaluate and improve wave models. These sessions are the first organized public presentations of the preliminary results. This paper is an introduction to the experiment and presentations.

INTRODUCTION

This paper introduces the two sessions in Oceans '82 on the ARSLOE wave experiment. Although ARSLOE was really three experiments in one, only that part related to waves is being presented in these Oceans '82 sessions. The other major experiment components were related to remote sensing of (a) ocean fronts and (b) land cover. The experiment was hosted jointly by the U.S. Army Corps of Engineers, Coastal Engineering Research Center (CERC), and the National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration, National Ocean Survey (NOS). Joint management was by Dr. C. L. Vincent of CERC and the author. Many other organizations participated as shown in Table 1. Mr. David Lichy of CERC was field coordinator.

The purposes of the Wave part of ARSLOE were:

1. Intercomparing the measurements from available sensor systems;
2. Developmental tests for new type directional wave measurement systems;
3. Testing shallow water wave models;
4. Studying fetch limited wave growth.

ARSLOE was held in the area off Duck, North Carolina, from October 6 to November 30, 1980, and centered on the Field Research Facility (FRF) of CERC. This location has relatively smooth bottom topography and a fairly straight coastline without nearby inlets or islands to complicate wave growth and propagation computations. The 600-meter-long instrumented pier and computer facilities at the FRF were major advantages.

The organization of the experiment has been quite informal. CERC and NOS put together a basic plan, funded a basic set of measurements and analyses, and invited others to make suggestions and participate. Final operating details and deployment locations were worked out in a meeting of the Principal Investigators on July 27, 1980, at CERC. After the experiment was completed and participants had had an opportunity to review the data they had gathered, a meeting was held February 18 to 20, 1981, at Virginia Beach, Virginia, to plan analyses and data exchange. Preliminary comparisons of data and analyses were discussed at a September 17, 1981, workshop in Berkeley, California, following the Directional Wave Spectra Applications meeting. It was agreed

TABLE 1
ARSLOE PARTICIPATION

Canada Center for Inland Waters (CCIW)
National Aeronautics and Space Administration (NASA)
Langley Research Center
Wallops Flight Center
National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration (NOAA)
National Ocean Survey
National Weather Service
Office of Ocean Technology and Engineering Services
Wave Propagation Laboratory
Atlantic Oceanographic and Meteorological Laboratories
Pacific Marine Environmental Laboratory
National Oceanographic Data Center
Naval Research Laboratory (NRL)
U.S. Army Corps of Engineers (COE)
Coastal Engineering Research Center (CERC)
Waterways Experiment Station (WES)
Environmental Research Institute of Michigan (ERIM)
Johns Hopkins Applied Physics Laboratory (JHAPL)
Kyushu University (KU)
Marine Environments Corporation (MEC)
Merides Company, France (M)
North Carolina State University (NCSU)
Norwegian Hydrodynamic Laboratories (NHL)
Scripps Institute of Oceanography (SIO)
TSI, Incorporated (TSI)
University of Florida (UF)
University of Rhode Island (URI)
Woods Hole Oceanographic Institution (WHOI)

there to present preliminary results of ARSLOE at Oceans '82. A series of informal reports have been used to communicate and coordinate among the investigators. All data are being stored in a special ARSLOE archive at the NOAA National Oceanographic Data Center. All participants have agreed to publish their material individually with no group control.

THE EXPERIMENT

The experiment included offshore and inshore measurements as shown in Table 2 and Figures 1 and 2. The offshore measurements were mostly made with buoys and aircraft. Inshore, the primary systems were bottom mounted pressure and current arrays and staffs. Coastal-based radar systems covered one or both regions.

The general arrangement of the measurement network was based on an underlying cross-shaped grid of wave measurements. Waveriders and XERB extended the row of wave staffs along the pier seaward to 36 km offshore where the water depth was about 30 m. Waveriders were also placed 15 km north and south of this row at 12 km offshore making the cross. The Waveriders were carefully calibrated and moored similarly. This provided detailed high-quality measurements from shallow to deep and the homogeneity of the waves parallel to the shore.

To provide better intercomparisons, there was an attempt to concentrate the small directional buoys at the center of the cross at 12 km which was also the center point for most aircraft flights. Similarly, the shallow water directional sensors were centered just north of the pier. Because the many systems used so many of the available standard Waverider radio frequencies, the Wadibuoy had to be shifted to an alternate higher frequency which resulted in shortening its range so that it had to be placed closer to shore.

Three Waveriders were deployed at the 12 km location prior to deployment of the directional sensors on September 25, 1980, to estimate the variability that could be expected due to the lack of co-location. Since these measurements began before the official October 6 start of ARSLOE, they have come to be known as ARSLOE ALPHA. After ARSLOE officially ended on November 30, several buoys and the CODAR were continued in operation for varying times.

Several other parameters were measured besides waves. Winds were to be measured at the pier, at 12 km, 20 km, and 36 km. Unfortunately, the wind measuring buoy at 20 km was vandalized early in the experiment and could not be repaired. Other weather information was measured at the pier, and 36 km locations. Seabed characteristics and bathymetry were determined from side scan sonar, seismic profiler, grab samplers, and a sled with stadia rod. Surface and subsurface currents were measured by several different systems at a few locations. Tides were measured at the pier.

TABLE 2
MEASUREMENT SYSTEMS USED IN ARSLOE

SENSOR TYPE	NUMBER OPERATED	ORGANIZATIONS*
Waverider	8 Systems	COE, NOAA, CCIW
Baylor Staff	8 Systems	COE
Pressure Array	1 System	SIO
Pressure Transducer	2 Systems	COE
Pressure and Current	4 Systems	COE, WHOI, UF
E-M Current	3 Systems	COE, NHL
Pitch-Roll-Heave Buoys	5 Systems	+NOAA, CCIW, NCSU, N, URI
Cloverleaf Buoy	1 Buoy	KU
Side Looking Airborne Radar	23 Flights #	COE, NOAA
Synthetic Aperture Radar	4 Flights	COE
Surface Contouring Radar	4 Flights	NASA
Ground Based Imaging Radar	1 System	COE
Δ K Radar	4 Flights	NASA, NRL
HF Radar (CODAR)	1 System	NOAA
CW Radar	1 System	NRL
Laser	6 Flights	NOAA, NASA
Downward Directed Sonar	1 System	JHAPL
Stillwell Camera	1 System	JHAPL
Air Temperature	4 Systems	NOAA, COE
Air Pressure	2 Systems	NOAA, COE
Anemometer	6 Systems	NRL, NOAA, CCIW, COE, JHAPL, TSI
Tide	2 Systems	NOAA, COE
Water Temperature	4 Systems	COE, NRL
Conductivity	1 System	COE
Side Scan Sonar	1 System	COE
Grab Sampler	24 Samples	COE
Seismic Reflection	1 System	COE
Sea Sled and Stadia	1 System	COE

* Abbreviations are as shown in Table 1.

+ Known respectively as XERB, MET, NC, Wadibuoy, and ENDECO Wave-track.

Airborne Systems operated on one or more of the following aircraft: NOAA P-3, NASA P-3, NRL P-3, U.S. Marine Corps RF-4B, U.S. Army OV-1.

Most of these in-water systems were deployed and tended routinely by the NOAA vessel LAIDLAY which operated out of the U.S. Coast Guard Station at Oregon Inlet. The University of Delaware vessel CAPE HENLOPEN spent about 2 weeks on site as a base for the Cloverleaf buoy which operated in a tethered mode. She also handled heavier buoys and otherwise assisted when not operating the Cloverleaf.

As much of the data as feasible was telemetered to the FRF computer where it could be monitored in near-real-time. At the computer, the data were generally digitized at 1/2-second intervals and recorded in both digital and analog form. The general routine was to operate the systems for 1 hour every 6 hours when the waves were low and for 1 hour every 2 hours when the waves were determined by the Coordinator to be high enough to be interesting. During some aircraft overflights, the systems were operated continuously.

RESULTS

After looking at their data, the Principal Investigators established a few time periods to be analyzed in detail. One of these (October 23 to 27) is especially interesting because a sharp frontal system with gale force winds and accompanying large waves occurred when most of the

- WAVERIDER △ METEOROLOGICAL
- * CLOVERLEAF ● PITCH-ROLL-HEAVE

Figure 1 - Offshore Buoy Locations

measurement systems were operable. This case has come to be known as the ARSLOE storm.

Two special sessions have been organized at Oceans '82 to summarize the results of this experiment to date, most of the results being presented are still preliminary. The first session will primarily cover the intercomparison of different wave measurement systems in deeper water. The second session, chaired by Dr. Vincent, will focus on nearshore data and theoretical advances that have resulted from ARSLOE.

Figure 2 - Nearshore Sensor Locations